

Mechanisms and applications of wind turbine blade waste in cementitious composites: A review

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ABSTRACT

The cement and concrete industry play vital roles in global and local economies, and urgent measures are required to minimize carbon emissions. Utilizing end-of-life (EoL) wind turbine blades (WTB) in cementitious matrices—whether as fiber reinforcement, aggregate replacement, or binder material—represents an innovative solution to mitigate environmental impacts. This offers potential due to their rich calcium, silicon, and aluminum content in glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP). The current review paper highlights the fundamental properties of WTBW (waste from wind turbine blades). Waste-cement reaction mechanisms and physical/mechanical properties of WTBW-incorporated cementitious materials are identified and discussed. Environmental implications and future research directions are also discussed. Findings suggest that fibers with epoxy resin from WTBW can increase water absorption by changing pore structure, hindering cement hydration and long-term strength. Epoxy resin may lower pH through hydroxyl ion consumption, delaying hydration, extending setting time, and reducing early strength. Meanwhile, the incorporation of WTBW in cementitious materials includes two main concepts—reinforcement (as fibers) or replacement (as powder, sand, or coarse aggregates). Low WTBW replacement levels ($\leq 10\%$) yield optimized mechanical performance, with decreasing performance at higher dosages. This work emphasizes the promise of WTBW in sustainable construction materials.

1. Introduction

Cement and concrete industries are vital to both global and local economies. However, this sector is also responsible for 7% of the worldwide carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions from human activities [1]. With more than 4.4 billion tons of concrete produced annually worldwide, more efforts are needed to drive the cement and concrete industries—one of the most carbon-intensive sectors—towards carbon neutrality [2]. A carbon-mitigation method uses wastes—such as wind turbine blades (WTB)—at the end of their service life to replace raw materials in construction materials manufacturing.

Over the past two decades, wind energy has emerged as a highly

promising renewable energy source, experiencing substantial growth in installed capacity. The capacity has surged from 7,600 MW in 1998 to an impressive 364,270 MW by 2014 [3]. The capacity is expected to continue to increase, although rates may vary in different geographical areas [4]. China will need to process 40% of global blade waste, while Europe and the United States will handle 25% and 16%, respectively. Europe, having installed large-scale wind farms earlier, will encounter end-of-life waste issues first. Globally, there will be more than 2,000,000 tons of end-of-life (EoL) blades needing to be processed in 2050 [4]. Growing concern over the disposal of EoL WTB is becoming a significant global problem. Currently, a substantial portion of EoL WTB waste is disposed of through incineration or landfilling, resulting in a waste of

Abbreviations: WTBS, Wind turbine blades; EoL, End-of-life; WTBW, Wind Turbine Blade Waste; FRP, Fiber reinforced polymer; GFRP, glass fiber-reinforced polymer; CFRP, carbon fiber-reinforced polymer; GF, Glass fiber; C–(A)–S–H, Calcium (Aluminate) Silicate Hydrates; C–S–H, Calcium Silicate Hydrates; XRD, X-ray Diffraction; FTIR, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy; TGA, Thermogravimetric analysis; ITZ, Interfacial transition zone; XCT, X-ray computed tomography; SEM, Scanning electron microscopy; ASR, Alkali-silicate reaction; RCM, Rapid chloride migration; GWP, Global warming potential; LCA, Life cycle assessments; GHG, Greenhouse gas.

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resources and additional expenses for producers and suppliers of WTB [5].

Landfilling of wind turbine blade waste (WTBW) should be avoided due to the long-term environmental impact, limited landfill space, and the need to pursue more sustainable and circular waste management solutions. The optimum recycling concept is aligned with obtaining recyclates of the same properties as the raw materials at a low cost and in the most environmentally friendly way. These methods can reclaim fibers, fillers, and resin from the FRP material, but technical barriers and commercialization challenges can lead to more landfilling and incineration activities. Therefore, alternative recycling methods have been explored, including three dominant recycling technologies (shown in Fig. 1): chemical (solvolysis), thermal (pyrolysis), and mechanical (grinding) recycling. The chemical recycling process, particularly solvolysis, can efficiently recycle mineral compounds, fibers, and resin chemicals [6]. The key advantage of solvolysis is the recovery of clean fibers in their full length and highly retained tensile strength [7], with simultaneous recovery of the resin (oligomers or polymers) [8]. However, large-scale low efficiency, large amounts of solvents, and ecotoxic gas emissions raise concerns regarding solvolysis use, while strict technical requirements raise concerns regarding investment and running costs [9]. Pyrolysis of recycling WTBW offers a promising avenue for sustainable disposal, transforming the materials into valuable resources through a thermochemical process [10]. Pyrolysis is an economically sound process for recycling carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) (high value) because it is an easily scaled-up technique to reach multi-tonne capacity [7]. Similar to solvolysis, fiber products of pyrolysis may retain oxidation residue or char [11]. Thus, it requires optimization of the temperature and time of the reaction to maintain the mechanical properties and surface chemistry at a maximum quality. During pyrolysis, potential combustible gas leakage from waste treatment chambers is a key point to consider [12]. Mechanical recycling is a better option, considering the low price of virgin glass [8]. Mechanical grinding is identified as the most widely used recycling option and pre-treatment for many other recycling options, thanks to its efficient technology and low production cost. The energy needed for mechanical recycling is significantly lower than chemical recycling (21–91 MJ/kg) and thermal recycling (24–30 MJ/kg), with an estimated range of 0.1–4.8 MJ/kg [13,14]. However, the low quality of fiber recovery and fiber shape is an unexpected output [15]. Recycled fibers also contain other impurities, including polymers, contaminants, paint, coatings, etc. In addition, fine

dust is released into the surrounding atmosphere during the grinding process, which raises environmental concerns [16]. Thus, a more direct and urgent solution is required before advances in recycling options are implemented.

Only recently has the option of utilizing WTBW in cement/concrete matrices been explored within the research field [17]. The high calcium (Ca), silicon (Si), and aluminum (Al) contents found in WTBW, which constitute the primary reactive element of cementitious materials, offer significant potential for utilization in construction applications, whether in the form of powder, aggregate, or fiber [18,19]. The low-end application of WTBW as sustainable aggregate and fiber in concrete has been previously explored [20]. On the one hand, the real density of WTBW aggregate, approximately 1.6 kg/dm³, was obtained after the mechanical recycling technique, similar to the value of a lightweight aggregate. Typically, those recycled WTBW aggregates are used to produce lightweight concrete. On the other hand, the bridging effect of WTBW fibers mainly increases the tensile and flexural strength of concrete and provides post-cracking toughness [21]. The fibers act as rigid elements embedded in the cementitious matrix, reducing concrete shrinkage. Indeed, a better understanding of the mechanism and limitations of using WTBW waste (WTBW) as cement, aggregate, or fiber in cement/concrete mixtures is vital to a better product. Comprehensive research is needed on how different components of WTBW influence 1) the reaction process (how the major components interact with the cementitious environment) and 2) the final properties of the cementitious matrix (how the WTBW influences the mechanical properties). These two critical questions remain insufficiently addressed in the literature, highlighting the need for a systematic review to guide the development of WTBW-containing cementitious composites.

This paper aims to provide a mechanistic understanding of using WTBW in a cementitious matrix. It examines the properties of WTBW, including both fibers and resins, as well as the characteristics of cementitious systems incorporating WTBW (Section 3). The reaction mechanism of WTBW-containing cementitious materials and factors limiting WTBW application in the cementitious matrix are discussed in Section 4. Two major concepts (reinforcement and replacement) of using WTBW in the cementitious matrix are reviewed in Section 5 in terms of its mechanical properties. Subsequently, the comparison against surrogate GFRP and WTBW-containing cementitious matrix and the extended scenarios of WTBW application in non-clinker composites are discussed in Section 6. Finally, the environmental impact of WTBW-

Fig. 1. Recycling methods of wind turbine blades.

containing concrete and future perspectives is presented in Section 7. Besides the transition from waste material to new cementitious composites, this review identifies critical research gaps and offers perspectives on further advancements in this field.

2. Methodology

We performed a literature review based on the methodology as described by Tyurkay et al.[22] (Fig. 2).

2.1. Search strategy and selection criteria

After defining the purpose of this research and formulating the research questions with the protocol as in Steps 1 and 2 in Fig. 2, we identified the keywords to retrieve literature. We used the DTU Findit platform (DTU Library, n.d.), which provides up-to-date open access and licensed content from DTU (<https://findit.dtu.dk/en/about/providers>) and other sources, including Elsevier, Scopus, Taylor & Francis, and Web of Science (WoS).

Iteratively in 2024, we searched using the keywords “End-of-life wind turbine blades”, “Wind turbine blade waste”, “Physical properties of Wind turbine blade waste”, “Chemical properties of Wind turbine blade waste”, “Glass fiber in concrete”, “Epoxy resin in concrete”, “Wind turbine blade waste in concrete”, “Wind turbine blade waste in cementitious materials”, “Environment impact of Wind turbine blade waste”, “LCA of Wind turbine blade waste in concrete”, and “LCA of waste materials”, which we interpreted as “kw: End-of-life AND wind AND turbine AND blades”, “kw: Wind AND turbine AND blade AND waste”, “kw: Physical properties AND Wind AND turbine AND blade AND waste”, “kw: Chemical properties AND Wind AND turbine AND blade AND waste”, “kw: Glass AND fiber AND concrete”, “kw: Epoxy AND resin AND concrete”, “kw: Carbon AND fiber AND concrete”, “kw: Wind AND turbine AND blade AND waste AND concrete”, “kw: Wind AND turbine AND blade AND waste AND cementitious materials”, “kw: Environmental impact AND Wind AND turbine AND blade AND waste”, “kw: LCA AND Wind AND turbine AND blade AND concrete”, and “kw: LCA AND waste AND materials”, respectively. Our search yielded 21,638 hits, with individual keyword results as follows: 120, 223, 11, 6308, 1880, 9800, 23, 2, 4, and 3310.

2.2. Data analysis and synthesis

To determine which studies to include, we evaluated their quality based on several factors. Our selection criteria, defined in Step 2 (Fig. 2), were guided by specific research questions. We classified the studies based on whether they explored the basic properties or performance of WTBW concrete and assessed their relevance to WTBW in concrete or cementitious materials. Our filtering process involved reading each article in three stages. We examined the title and abstract and then reviewed the introduction and conclusion, which mentioned the mineralogical properties of WTBW materials or specific WTBW reinforcement or replacement in the cementitious matrix. Finally, we reviewed the entire article, extracting the mineralogical properties of WTBW materials, such as XRD, XRF, and FTIR data, as well as the physical properties of WTBW-containing cementitious composites, including compressive strength, flexural strength, and elastic modulus. Following this thorough and iterative process and eliminating duplicates, we identified 127 studies that met our criteria (with specific data). Those data were prepared to the Synthesis step.

Step 5 Synthesis: The study’s synthesis focused on detailed information on the properties of WTBW, the mechanism of using WTBW in cementitious matrices, and the mechanical properties of WTBW-containing composites. The data were grouped into two subject categories: (1) WTBW material (Section 3): All mineralogical data are summarized, including crystalline structures, elemental distribution, and IR spectra, to provide a comprehensive overview of the material. (2) WTBW-containing composites (Sections 4 and 5): First, the chemical reactions of each WTBW component (glass fiber and epoxy resin) are summarized to understand the interactions between WTBW materials and the cementitious matrix. Next, the literature on the physical properties of WTBW-containing cementitious composites is synthesized to compare the changes in these properties.

3. End-of-life wind turbine blade waste

The most integral part of WTB is the fiber components, which contribute to the high stiffness of the product. Fibers can be glass, carbon, hybrid fiber, and natural fibers [23,24]. Typically, WTB contains up to 75 wt% of glass-resin composites, which is the volume of waste. Therefore, this paper predominantly focuses on the glass-resin part of the waste, which mainly influences the hydration process of

Fig. 2. Overall approach for literature review.

cementitious materials by the glass fiber and epoxy resin chemistry. Detailed information is provided in the Supplementary Materials, including glass fiber, epoxy resin, and the mixture of glass-resin polymer.

The chemical compositions of glass fiber in WTBW may vary because different glass fiber types influence its contents. X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) is normally applied to analyse the glass fiber (GF) from incinerated WTBW. The box plot chemical compositions and detailed information on GF are presented in Fig. 3 (a). Nearly 35 wt% of GF oxide composition is SiO_2 , followed by around 30 wt% CaO and 10 wt% Al_2O_3 oxide compositions. Minor traces of MgO and Na_2O can also be spotted. The crystalline structure of GF is usually determined by X-ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis, while the spectral properties are by Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). XRD and FTIR patterns are illustrated in Fig. 3 (b) and (c). The crystalline structure of GF is mainly amorphous silica (SiO_2).

The elemental composition of epoxy resin is determined by combined thermogravimetric-infrared (TG-FTIR) experiments. Variations in volatile content are exhibited in Fig. 3(d). The major elements in epoxy resin are carbon (C), oxygen (O), and hydrogen (H), regardless of their production resources. High carbon content is expected since epoxy resin

is a partially organic material. The XRD pattern and FTIR spectrum of epoxy resin are illustrated in Fig. 3(e) and (f). The humps of epoxy resin show the order degree of aromatic epoxide ring structure [25]. Table 1 shows the functional groups of epoxy resin present in the WTBW. The hydroxyl group [26,27], amine group [28], and thiol group [29] are also common in the epoxy resin used for WTBW manufacturing. The oxygen in the WTBW is generally in hydroxyl and epoxy groups [26]. As a curing agent, amine reacts with epoxy resin through a ring-opening reaction to form secondary amine. Then, the secondary amine reacts with epoxy resin to form the following substance with multiple hydroxyl structures. For the thiol group, it is a toughening agent by thiol-ene reaction for epoxy resin [29].

4. WTBW reaction mechanism in cementitious matrices

4.1. General reaction mechanism

The reaction mechanism of WTBW's main components, i.e., GF, CF, and epoxy resin, when mixed with concrete is discussed in this section. WTBW reaction in concrete is mainly characterized by a combined dissolution and gelation process. The dissolution of these materials is a

Fig. 3. (a) Chemical compositions in oxides weight percentage of the glass fiber from WTBW; (b) XRD patterns of GF [30]; (c) FTIR patterns of GF [30] (Reproduced by permission); (d) Chemical compositions in elemental weight percentage of the epoxy resin from WTBW; (e) XRD patterns of epoxy resin [25]; (f) FTIR spectrum of epoxy resin [31] (Reproduced by permission).

Table 1
Main functional groups of epoxy resin in WTBW.

Ref.	Functional groups	Typical structure	Remarks
[31,32]	Epoxy ring		Major functional group
[26,27]	Hydroxyl group		
[28]	Amine group		
[29]	Thiol group		
[25]	Carbonyl group		Mainly in the uncured epoxy resin
[31,33]	Anhydride group		

complex process that can be (i) congruent (surface-controlled/stoichiometric release of ions), (ii) incongruent (diffusion-controlled/leaching/selective/non-stoichiometric release), or (iii) dissolution, involving selective dissolution and congruency [34]. Moreover, the dissolution and gelation kinetics depend on the fiber (GF or CF) compositions [35] and functional groups (mainly from epoxy resin) in the pore solutions.

4.1.1. Chemical reactions of glass fiber in cementitious matrix

Within a concrete environment (typical pH > 11), the dissolution of GF occurs predominantly by silicate (aluminate) network hydrolysis and dissociation of the silicate (aluminate) network into Si(OH)₄ or other silicate (aluminate) tetrahedral species [36]. As shown in eq. (1) the reaction of GF in a concrete system is a subset of sequential reactions, including (1) dissolution of metastable silica (alumina), (2) formation of nano-colloidal silica (alumina) sol, and (3) gelation of the sol [37].

Fig. 4 illustrates the dissolution process of GF, originating from WTBW, within concrete. The embedded GF consists of the amorphous silicate (aluminate) chain structure. The calcium or sodium ions are connected to the end of silicate (aluminate) chain end. It is widely accepted that, within an alkaline setting, hydroxyl (OH⁻) ions gradually attack the (≡Si-O-) bonds, leading to the gradual dissolution of the silica network. Exposure of GF to – high pH – concrete environment results in fiber dissolution into monomers of Si-O tetrahedra or Al-O tetrahedra, dimers of Si-O tetrahedral, and oligomers of the Si_nO_a(OH)_b (shown in eq. (2), where 2a+b=n [38].

The gelation (gel formation) process depends on the elemental ions in the pore solutions of the concrete matrix. Provided that the pH and temperature are controlled to prevent excessive saturation concerning aqueous silica (alumina), and when there are no calcium and sodium ions present, the dissolved components remain in the solution [39]. In other words, the concrete matrix incorporates glass fiber, resulting in Ca²⁺ consumption. Ca²⁺ (from concrete binder) reacts with the aqueous silica (alumina), forming the C-(A)-S-H gels [40,41]. The different silicate (aluminate) monomers (as shown in Fig. 4) can form a 3D structure of amorphous gels. The gel can keep getting stronger and altering its properties as its network structure shifts and becomes more stable over time [42]. This process may include additional cross-linking or other secondary interactions within the network.

4.1.2. Chemical reactions of epoxy resin in cementitious matrix

Reactions can also be triggered while mixing WTBW in a concrete matrix. Fig. 5 demonstrates the behaviors of functional groups from

Fig. 4. Dissolution of glass fiber under cementitious environment [36,37].

Fig. 5. Behaviors of functional groups from epoxy resin under cementitious environment. (L. Morsch et al. [43]; O. Faruk et al. [45]; L. Dubois et al. [46]; B. Alvarez et al. [48]; M. Smith et al. [47]; A. Francis et al. [49]).

epoxy resin within a concrete environment. As shown in Fig. 5, the functional groups from epoxy resin affect the pH significantly. First, the epoxide rings are the major functional groups in the WTBW. The ring-opening reaction consumes large amounts of hydroxyl ions, forming enantiomers [43]. Subsequently, the pH decreases in the pore solution of the cement/concrete matrix. The consumption of alkali shows the retarding effect of epoxy resin on the cement hydration process. When it comes to the practical application of epoxy resin in concrete, Zhang et al. [44] reported that the retarding effect of epoxy latexes on the cement hydration is linked to the interplay among epoxy particles, minerals within the cement clinker and the resulting hydration products. This relationship exhibited a pronounced reliance on the duration of the hydration process. Thereby, raw materials and epoxide groups (from the waste) have synergetic effects on the hydration process of WTBW-incorporating concrete.

Previous studies [26,27] also reported hydroxyl groups in epoxy resin utilized in WTBW parts. The hydroxyl groups of epoxy resin can form hydrogen bonds with water molecules in cement/concrete pore solution [45]. Such behavior can mitigate the incompatibility between the epoxy resin and cement/concrete matrix, potentially leading to strength gain for WTBW-concrete systems. Besides, the amine group (generally in a curing agent) and carbonyl group (normally in uncured epoxy) can stabilize under high pH conditions [46,47]. They have an insignificant impact on the cement hydration process. The thiol and anhydride functional groups constitute a minor fraction of epoxy resin [48,49]. The thiol group reacts with hydroxyl ions, forming thiolate ions. Anhydride group reacts with hydroxyl ions, forming a carboxylate ion and a corresponding alcohol. Therefore, these reactions may lead to pH decay of the pore solution causing retarding effect. The limited amount of these two functional groups may also have a negligible impact on the cement hydration process.

4.2. Factors limiting WTBW application in concrete matrices

In this review, 3 main factors were found that can be considered barriers to the application of WTBW in cementitious matrices:

- Water absorption by the WTBW in the mixture
- Reduction of pH of pore solution in the mixture
- Lack of compatibility between cement-based matrix and organic matters

Water availability is an important factor affecting hydration in concrete environments. Previous studies have reported that glass/carbon fibers have a limited influence on water consumption if encapsulated in a cement/concrete matrix [50,51] since both types are known as hydrophobic materials [52,53]. However, higher water absorption is often observed due to fibers affecting the pore structure evolution [50,51]. Although the epoxy resin present in WTBW has considerably lower water absorption than cement or natural aggregate [54], the hydroxyl group in epoxy resin bonds with water molecules via hydrogen bonding [55]. Therefore, epoxy resin may lead to lower water availability for the cement particles. Consequently, full hydration of cement is hindered by the limited water availability. The reaction products decrease with the lower water content. Limited availability of portlandite ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) results in lower formation of gels (e.g., calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H)), affecting the long-term concrete strength.

Another factor is the pH decrease of the pore solution in WTBW concrete due to the reaction between the epoxy resin and hydroxides. The pore solution creates the necessary physical and chemical setting for cement hydration. This environment facilitates the transfer of calcium, silicon, and hydroxyl ions, which are released during the dissolution of cement clinker, into the resulting hydration products, i.e., C-S-H gels [56]. The kinetics of early cement hydration are affected by the pH of the pore solution. This includes the dissolution of cement clinker and the precipitation of reaction products. WTBW fibrous parts may not influence the pH of the cement pore solution because of hydrophobic properties [52,53]. However, the functional groups (as mentioned in Section 4.1.2) of epoxy resin possibly consumes certain amounts of hydroxyl ions, leading to a decrease in pH and impeding the hydration process. Finer WTBW particles increase the exposure of the epoxide ring to hydroxyl ions within the pore solution. The retarding effect from epoxy resin being present in the mix increases the setting time of cement [57]. The epoxy resin also tends to adsorb onto the cement particles, further inhibiting the hydration process. Generally, the retarding action of epoxy resin reduces the early strength of cement or concrete matrix. Overall, the epoxy resin within WTBW reduces the early pH, leading to increased concrete setting time and reduced early strength. Such behavior is a limitation that needs to be cautiously considered regarding the potential application of WTBW into cementitious systems.

Using WTBW in cementitious materials triggers the issue of compatibility between cement-based matrix and organic matters (especially epoxy resin). Epoxy resin and cement-based materials seem incompatible since the solvent affects the cement hydration and setting

[58]. The epoxy resin decreases the nucleation rate of cement clinker leading to the retarding effect on cement setting [44]. Incorporation of epoxy resin into the cement matrix introduces voids and/or pores in the [59,60] and also renders the interfacial transition zone (ITZ) (between waste and binder matrix) weaker [18]. Consequently, the mechanical properties of epoxy resin-cement matrix systems are usually lower than pure OPC matrix. Utilizing waste as reinforcement may accommodate challenges in achieving a uniform distribution of the fibrous parts within the concrete matrix. It is worth noting that previous studies show that uniformly-distributed fibrous materials provide nucleation sites for cement hydration [61,62]. Uniformly-distributed fibers can also assist in controlling plastic shrinkage cracking. Fibers can bridge the cracks, preventing their propagation and reducing their width [63]. However, swelling or agglomeration of fibrous WTBW, especially at small particle sizes, may result in internal defects of the cement/concrete matrix, eventually decreasing strength [63].

In addition to the mentioned three factors (water absorption, pH, and compatibility) influencing the application of WTBW in cementitious materials under normal curing conditions, the following factors also impact the cement-based reactions, which might not be in the ambient conditions:

- Curing temperature of WTBW-containing cementitious matrix
- Effect of pressure on reaction equilibrium
- Chemical behavior when WTBW interacts with different additives
- Particle size and distribution of the WTBW

Curing temperature has an important effect on WTBW in cementitious materials [64]. Higher temperatures speed up the dissolution process of glass content in WTBW, accelerating the hydration process of WTBW-containing cementitious composite. However, if the temperature is too high, the heat can break down the epoxy resin, which might weaken the composite over time. Besides, pressure also affects the performance of WTBW in cementitious materials [65]. Higher pressure can improve the packing of particles, reduce voids, and make the material denser, which can increase strength. Too much pressure might damage the WTBW (as fiber) or cause uneven distribution in the matrix, leading to weaker areas. Certain additives might react with the epoxy resin or glass content in WTBW [66]. For instance, additives such as pozzolans (high Al content) may affect the hydration process of WTBW powder (high Si content), which leads to more formation of C(N)-A-S-H gels, influencing the setting time, strength, and durability [42]. The particle size and distribution of WTBW, whether as fibers or powder, play a crucial role in cementitious materials [67]. Smaller particles can fill voids more effectively and have pozzolanic activity, increasing the density and strength of the cementitious matrix, but they may also require more water due to their higher surface area. Larger particles, on the other hand, contribute to mechanical reinforcement but may lead to weaker bonding if not evenly distributed.

5. Properties of WTBW-containing composites

Considering the available literature, incorporation of the WTBW mechanically shredded (WTBW-MS) material into cementitious formulations can be divided into two main concepts, including the reinforcement, where the shredded fibrous mix or selected macrofibers are used as additional material to the cementitious mix and the replacement, where concrete/mortar main constituents (i.e., sand, cement, and coarse aggregates) are partially replaced by the WTBW. Therefore, the literature findings below are separated into two conceptual distinctions: reinforcement and replacement.

5.1. Reinforcement concept

When used for structural reinforcement purposes, fibers possess adequate tensile strength. They are usually large (fiber diameter ~ 0.3

mm), serving as crack control elements or structural reinforcement substituting steel rebar reinforcement [68,69]. Fibers of an average diameter lower than 0.3 mm can be categorized as microfibers and serve as plastic or drying shrinkage-controlling elements (ASTM C1116 [70]). Adopting a similar strategy and conceptual design, fibrous elements, mainly consisting of GF and epoxy resin, reclaimed from WTBW could be a worth investigating option. The tensile strength of WTBW-based GFs is known to exceed 2000 MPa after pyrolysis [71], implying there is a breeding ground to be used as reinforcing elements. The effect of WTBW on concrete properties as fiber reinforcement is summarized in Fig. 6 including workability, compressive strength, and flexural strength. Meanwhile, the influence of WTBW on elastic modulus and toughness is also discussed. The detailed discussion is presented as follows.

5.1.1. Workability

The fresh properties of concrete directly influence long-term strength and durability; hence, it is essential to evaluate the performance of fresh concrete with the integration of WTBW. The workability of concrete refers to its ease of handling, placing, and compacting in its fresh state. It measures how easily the concrete can be mixed, transported, and finished without segregation or bleeding. Several factors can affect the workability of concrete, such as the water-to-cement ratio (w/c), the size and gradation of the particles, the shape, surface roughness, and absorption of the aggregates or fibers (when incorporated), and the desired mix proportions [72]. Slump testing is usually applied to quantify the workability of the fresh concrete mix and flow spread diameter for mortars. When incorporating fibrous elements within the cement mix, a reduction in slump is observed, implying a deteriorated workability state. Such behavior is attributed to various factors, including the conglomeration of fibrous particles, leading to the accumulation of water around the surface of the fibers and the increased specific surface area, which again raises the water demand and, thus, reduces the water available for cement hydration. [73–75]. In addition, the random nature of the fibers' morphology and roughness, paired with the random aspect ratios, is an additional factor contributing to reducing the workability of the concrete mixture.

Mixing WTBW fibrous elements in fresh concrete raises workability issues and has drawn interest in the research community. The results are summarized in Fig. 6(a). Xu et al. [76] conducted slump tests on concrete specimens reinforced with macrofibrous elements recycled from WTBW to quantify how the workability of the fresh mix is affected. The selected macrofibers (predominantly mix of GF and epoxy resin) had an average length of 47.2 mm and an aspect ratio of 49. The aspect ratio is the fiber length divided by the thinnest dimension). Their findings revealed an average slump reduction of 28% ($\pm 7.7\%$) per 1% vol. waste addition. Fu et al. [77] incorporated macrofibers with an average length of 89.7 mm and an aspect ratio of 114 into the concrete mix, reporting a slump loss of 36% ($\pm 1.4\%$) per 1% vol. waste added as reinforcement media. Cuesta et al. [20] used shorter fibrous elements with an average length of 13 mm (aspect ratio: 18) into the cementitious mix, demonstrating an average reduction in slump equal to 7.1% ($\pm 2.2\%$) per 1% vol. waste addition.

A reasonable trend of slump reduction with a growing percentage of added macro fibrous elements is primarily spotted. Comparing only the reinforcement cases (Xu et al. [76], Fu et al. [77], and Cuesta et al. [20]), a correlation between the average length (and the corresponding aspect ratio) and the magnitude of slump reduction can be observed. The detrimental effect of higher length and aspect ratio on the workability of the fresh concrete mix can be noted. Slump reduction is lower for the same reinforcement levels, i.e., the percentage of added micro fibrous elements in the mix, when shorter elements are encapsulated. Fig. 6(b) designates the almost linear correlation between the average length of the elements used in the concrete mix and the reduction reported in slump testing (flow diameter) values.

Fig. 6. (a) Effect of WTBW fiber reinforcement by volumetric addition, (b) Effect of WTBW fiber reinforcement by fiber length on concrete workability; (c) Effect of WTBW element reinforcement on concrete compressive strength; (d) Effect of WTBW element reinforcement on concrete flexural strength.

5.1.2. Compressive strength

Uniaxial compression is one of the key testing parameters, designating the strength of a cementitious material. A limited series of tests have been published within the available literature investigating the properties of cementitious materials containing WTBW fibrous elements as reinforcement. A certain optimal limit has been reported beyond which increasing the added waste volume reduces compressive strength [77]. This is attributed to the cumulative effect of multiple competitive mechanisms on material behavior. More specifically, these mechanisms include fibrous elements (1) absorbing a certain amount of free water, reducing the water/cement ratio of the mix (thereby influencing the mechanical strength) [78]; (2) constraining the development of shrinkage cracking, acting as “bridge” at the interfaces during crack opening [79,80]; (3) introducing weak interfaces between the fibrous elements and concrete [81]. Baturkin et al [18] reported a compressive strength reduction, less than <5%, when such elements (1.75 vol%) were added into the concrete mix as reinforcement. Similar observations have been reported by Fu et al. [77], Xu et al. [76], and Cuesta et al. [20]. A limited, almost negligible, reduction in strength has been observed (<5% for 1% addition of fiber by volume of mix). Interestingly, even though the compressive strength is not significantly affected by adding fibrous elements, the strain at failure rises considerably, enhancing the concrete ductility [76,77,82]. Recycled WTBW macrofibers serve as a bridging component, transferring stress to the matrix and, therefore, increasing the concrete resistance against cracking (Xu et al [76], Fu et al. [77]). Most studies indicate a slim reduction in the compressing strength of cementitious products containing WTBW fibrous elements, except for Fu et al. [77], reporting a slight improvement (3.5 – 4.2%). The greatest rise was observed for 0.5% vol. addition in the concrete mix, where higher levels of reinforcement lead to lower gains in compressive strength. Hofmeister [83] added 3 mm wide and 30 mm long strips, cut off from WTB at 1 vol% of the mix. Since the strips were

cut parallel to the unidirectional fibers, the compressive strength of the concrete increased by 15.6% after 7 days. In addition, Hofmeister also substituted pyrolysis-treated WTBW strips of similar dimensions as the untreated ones at 1 vol% of the mix and noticed a 27% drop in compressive strength after 7 days. The experimental results analyzed in this paragraph are summarized in Fig. 6(c). Overall, the 0.5 to 1 vol% addition as fiber reinforcement in the concrete mix will have competitive compressive strength with control samples without WTBW fiber.

5.1.3. Flexural strength

The predominant benefit of utilizing fibrous components as reinforcement media within cementitious materials is the improvement of properties such as tensile strength, flexural strength, impact resistance, and durability [84]. The effect of WTBW element reinforcement on concrete flexural strength is shown in Fig. 6(d). Reinforced specimens sustain flexural loading with crack propagation for a longer period compared to the reference material. This is attributed to the macrofiber “bridging effect”, enhancing the capacity to resist loading beyond crack initiation. The cracks propagate and intersect several fibrous elements, which mitigate the opening of cracks due to this bridging effect [76]. According to the state-of-the-art report published by ACI [85], it is also worth noting that longer fiber lengths, i.e. macrofibers, provide greater resistance to tensile/flexural failure. Baturkin [18] reported a rise in concrete flexural strength via adding WTBW fibrous elements (<300 μ m in diameter and <3mm in length) within the mix. The flexural strength of the WTBW-bearing concrete specimens increased by 5% and 15% when reinforced with 1% and 1.75% by vol. of concrete, respectively.

Xu et al. [76] incorporated longer fibrous elements (average length of 47.2 mm) in the concrete mix, suggesting a 37.85% improvement in the flexural strength of concrete beams at 2.5% reinforcement levels. The improved flexural strength was attributed to the increased residual strength of concrete at the post-peak deflection softening branch of the

flexural load–deflection curve. Similarly, Fu et al. [77] reinforced their concrete mix with WTBW oriented selected long fibrous elements. The corresponding average length was 89.7mm, akin to longitudinal reinforcements in the concrete beams. The results of the study revealed considerable improvement in concrete flexural strength. More specifically, a 15.73%, 82.82%, and 120.25% gain in flexural strength was observed compared to the reference/control beams for 0.5%, 1.0%, and 1.5% by vol. of added WTBW material, respectively. Higher vol. percentages of WTBW fiber lead to higher flexural strength in general.

5.1.4. Elastic modulus

The elastic modulus can be extracted from the ascending branch of the stress–strain curve in compression testing of samples. Xu et al [76] concluded that while addition of fibrous WTBW negatively affects the peak compressive strength of the mortar, the ductile behavior is improved because of fibrous material addition and the elastic modulus of the mixture is enhanced up until a certain critical value of WTBW addition. The most significant increase in the elastic modulus was reported to be 12.43% at 0.5 vol% addition. Furthermore, 1 vol% addition resulted in an average reduction of ~7% in the elastic modulus. Fu et al. [77] demonstrated a similar finding: the elastic modulus was 3.42% greater than the relative mix at vol. additions of 0.5% and 1%. The smallest increase was 1.37% relative to the reference mixture at 1.5 vol % addition.

5.1.5. Toughness

Toughness is an indicator of the energy absorbed under stress, commonly calculated by the area under a load–deflection curve. Increasing the amount and size of WTBW in concrete can improve the toughness [76,77]. Hence, a more gradual softening behavior, typically observed in fiber-reinforced concrete elements, hints at larger energy absorption of concrete before failure. More specifically, Fu et al. [77] reported that the average toughness in the control group of specimens was only 0.97 J, while the corresponding values for specimens containing 0.5%, 1.0%, and 1.5% by vol. of WTBW were 82.3 J, 151.3 J, and 182.4 J, respectively. Similarly, Xu et al. [76] found the mean toughness of the reference sample to be 1.52 J; however, the addition of WTBW at 0.5%, 1.5%, and 2.5% improved the energy absorbed significantly to 24.91 J, 35.96 J, and 57.42 J respectively.

5.2. Replacement concept

The replacement concept in cement-based materials involves substituting three traditional components: (a) sand, (b) coarse aggregate, and (c) cement with WTBW to improve sustainability and potentially comparative material properties.

5.2.1. Sand replacement

In addition to concrete reinforcement concepts, replacement

concepts are also attracting growing interest among the research community. The potential of replacing part of the raw materials used within a concrete/mortar mix, i.e., cement, sand, and coarse aggregates, with GFRP waste has been extensively discussed in the relevant literature [86–89], demonstrating that similar research could be applied to the WTBW material. Today, only a limited number of relevant studies have been published.

Sand is an essential component in concrete mixtures, serving as a filler for the voids between coarse aggregates, promoting workability and ease of placement [72]. In addition, sand contributes to the strength build-up and cohesion of the concrete mix [90]. The type and amount of sand affect the water demand of concrete mixes. Properly graded sand enhances the bond between the cement paste and the coarse aggregates, improving compressive strength [91]. The effect of WTBW on concrete properties as sand replacement is summarized in Fig. 7 including compressive strength and flexural strength. Meanwhile, the influence of WTBW on bulk density and toughness is also discussed. The detailed discussion is presented as follows.

5.2.1.1. Compressive strength. The effect of partially replacing sand with pulverized waste (mechanically shredded powder) (WTBW-MSP) on the compressive strength of a cementitious material is presented in Fig. 7(a). The results correspond to experimental trials where mortar specimens were prepared [32,92]. To our knowledge, relevant data are unavailable for concrete specimens where WTBW-MSP replaced part of the sand. Fig. 7(a) indicates that replacing a part of sand with WTBW-MSP leads to a significant reduction in compressive strength.

This reduction in compressive strength can be attributed to a variety of factors, including:

- The inherently lower strength of WTBW-MSP particles when compared to natural sand
- A less robust interfacial bond between WTBW-MSP particles and cement paste, associated with the variable cylindrical shape of the particles, the fractions of inorganic and organic content within the WTB, and the size of the particles
- The presence of voids and an uneven distribution of WTBW-MSP particles within the cementitious mix, either due to an increase in the water content adjusted to maintain a similar flow to that of reference flow or due to poor morphology of the particles.

Oliveira et al. [32] reported that mortar incorporating WTBW-MSP would require a higher content of water to maintain the same flowability as the reference mixture, which leads to a 4% increase in the porosity of the mixture and, ultimately, a drop (around 18%) in 28-day compressive strength, even at limited replacement levels (7.5 wt%). The higher water requirement was attributed to the formation of water film around the rough textured and irregular granulometry of waste particles as opposed to the more round and smooth textured sand particles.

Fig. 7. Effect of sand replacement on the (a) compressive strength and (b) flexural strength of cementitious composites (mortar).

Rodin et al. [92] studied the effect of different-sized fractions (Large: 2mm < fiber size < 2.38mm; Medium: 1.41 mm < size < 2 mm; Small: 0.841 mm < size < 0.42 mm; Powder: size > 0.42mm) of WTBW-MSP on the cementitious mixture. The different fractions were sieved to classify them by size, and each group size, except for the powder, was evaluated using image analysis to determine their respective aspect ratios. The reports highlight that smaller particles reduce compressive strength due to the higher specific surface area of the particles requiring a higher binder percentage. Rodin et al. [92] also concluded that the filling effect creates a denser mix if the size fractions are deliberately selected. Consequently, the void volume and increased compressive strength can also be reduced.

Overall, 7.5 wt% of sand replacement might be a critical value for minimizing the decrease of compressive strength due to the high water absorption of WTBW fiber in the matrix.

5.2.1.2. Flexural strength. The flexural strength of cementitious mixtures, incorporating WTBW material as sand replacement, exhibits similar behavior to the compressive strength. A reduction in flexural strength of WTBW-containing mortar specimens has been reported by Oliveira et al. [32], with the percentage drop, though, being half as much as that of compressive strength. Rodin et al. [92] utilized different grades of WTBW after shredding and sieving (WTBW-MS) as sand replacement. The products of the sieving process were separated – based on size – into four groups: three groups of fibrous (passing sieve > 0.8mm) and one group of powdery (> 0.4 mm) material. It is important to clarify that fibrous elements used for sand replacement differ significantly in size, especially in length, compared to those used for reinforcement, as analyzed in the previous section. The positive effect of utilizing larger fibrous WTBW particles on the mortar's compressive strength was demonstrated. The results showed that incorporating fibrous parts, as a sand replacement, into the mortar mix, can lead to an increased or equivalent 7-day flexural strength compared to control specimens, except for the powdery scenario (flexural strength decreased by 30%). The group corresponding to the largest fibrous elements displayed the most significant improvement. The results are shown in Fig. 7 (b).

5.2.1.3. Bulk density. In addition to the workability, another property affected by the incorporation of WTBW is the bulk density of the cementitious mix (shown in Table 2).

Raw WTB density (1.2–2.0 g/cm³) is smaller than conventional concrete (2.4 g/cm³) or mortar (2.2 g/cm³), resulting in a density decay of the hardened, WTBW-containing cementitious mixture (Table 2). Oliveira et al. [32] demonstrated that a 7.5% volumetric replacement of sand with WTBW results in more than 10% decay of mortar density, owing to a material (sand density ~ 2.6 g/cm³) being replaced with a less dense one (WTB raw density ~ 1.6 g/cm³). This behavior is consistent with higher replacement levels (up to 37.5%).

5.2.1.4. Toughness. The literature concerning the effect of replacing fine aggregate with WTBW on the toughness of mixtures is scarce. Rodin et al. [92] conducted flexural tests on mortar bars with 3% by weight replacement of filler material of different size fractions to determine the toughness of samples based on a 'toughness index'. The first toughness index is computed as $I_2 = (A+B)/A$, whereby A represents the pre-peak-load area under the curve, and B presents the post-peak-load area under

the curve. The findings showed that the toughness index of samples without WTBW and those containing 3% powdery filler (below 420 μm) results in an approximate toughness index of 1, indicating little to no absorbing of energy post-peak-load. For the samples with the largest average-sized filler material (2 – 2.38 mm), the greatest increase in toughness was observed at a toughness index of 2.15, highlighting more than twice the toughness relative to the control mixture. The toughness index values for the medium-sized (1.41 – 2 mm) and small-sized (0.42 – 1.41 mm) filler waste replacements were reported to be 1.88 and 1.18, respectively, indicating a positive correlation between waste filler size fraction and amount of energy the samples can absorb.

5.2.2. Coarse aggregate replacement

As opposed to typical mechanical processing (grinding and crushing) methods, the utilization of WTBW as coarse aggregate (CA) has been applied by directly cutting WTBWs into larger pieces, comparable to typical CA sizes [18,82,93]. The effect of WTBW on concrete properties as CA replacement is summarized in Fig. 8 including workability, compressive strength, and flexural strength. Meanwhile, the influence of WTBW on elastic modulus and toughness is also discussed. The detailed discussion is presented as follows.

5.2.2.1. Workability. In addition to the reinforcement concept, where the majority of workability work has been presented, authors dealing with the replacement concept have also examined the workability changes while altering/replacing coarse aggregates with differently shaped WTBW materials.

As shown in Fig. 8(a), Yazdanbakhsh et al. [94] dissected parts originating from WTBW into macro fibrous elements of 100 mm length and 6 mm square cross-section (aspect ratio: 14.8) and, subsequently, utilized them as a coarse aggregate replacement as opposed to volumetric addition (reinforcement) within the concrete mix. The workability tests revealed a 20% decay when replacing 5% of the coarse aggregates (4% per 1% vol. coarse aggregate replacement). However, no flow loss was reported upon increasing the fiber content from 5% to 10% by vol. of coarse aggregate. Additional concrete slump tests were conducted, incorporating grooved instead of plain fibrous elements in the mix, addressing the potential effect of surface shape on workability.

5.2.2.2. Compressive strength. Baturkin et al. [18] prepared 20 mm cubes from EoL-WTBs to potentially replace CA in concrete specimens. The replacement volumes were 33%, 66%, and 100%. The results showed that, due to loss of angular surfaces, lower roughness and morphology of the cubes, the interlocking bond between the cementitious mix and the fillers was compromised, eventually leading to 50% reduction in compressive strength when the WTB-waste material replaced 2/3rd of the coarse aggregate fraction. A linear correlation was observed between the percentage of replacement and the percentage reduction in compressive strength. Baturkin et al. [18] also highlighted the retarding effect of organic cellulose present in the mix. Removing the cellulose from the WTBW resulted in a 19% drop in compressive strength, as opposed to 32%, with cellulose content at replacement levels of 33%. Similarly, Yazdanbakhsh et al. [82] dissected EoL-WTBs to create needles-like slender elements (plain and grooved), which were subsequently used as CA replacement media in the concrete mixtures (5% and 10%). Owing to the smaller replacement levels, the compressive strength was retained compared to the control specimens for both plain and grooved needles. A noteworthy observation was that, in the case of grooved needles, a record 7.2% rise in compressive strength was documented at 5% CA replacement. However, contradictory findings were reported for the 10% replacement, where encapsulating grooved needles led to a 4.6% reduction. The authors attributed this paradox to the potential transverse arrangement (weaker fiber direction) of fibers in this second mix. The results are illustrated in Fig. 8 (b).

Table 2
Effect of WTBW incorporation on the product bulk density.

Author	Produced material	Replacement (R)/ Reinforcement (A)	Product density (g/cm ³)
Rodin [92]	Mortar	Sand (R)	1.82 ~ 2.00
Oliveira [32]	Mortar	Sand (R)	1.2 ~ 1.75

Fig. 8. Effect of WTBW as coarse aggregate (CA) replacement on (a) slump drop; (b) compressive strength; (c) flexural strength of cementitious composites (concrete).

In summary, the high replacement of coarse aggregate by WTBW leads to a remarkable drop in compressive strength, around 10 wt% replacement might have a competitive compressive strength to control the matrix.

5.2.2.3. Flexural strength. Baturkin et al. [18] proved that replacing part of the CA volume WTBW detracts concrete flexural strength. A 33 vol% replacement reduces flexural strength by 31%, while an additional 33% by vol. replacement (66%) resulted in a further 11% decrease. Replacing the entire volume of CA ultimately resulted in a 43% accumulated loss in concrete flexural strength, signifying a severe degradation in flexural strength compared to the reference/control specimens. This drop in flexural strength was attributed to the uniform size, surface roughness, and shape of the recycled WTBW elements. Yazdanbakhsh et al. [82] conducted 3-point bending tests to investigate the effect of incorporating WTBW as CA replacement on the material flexural strength, adopting smaller CA replacement percentages (5% and 10%). The results demonstrated a negligible drop in flexural strength (~5–7%) to that of the control specimens upon 5% and 10% by vol. of CA replacement. The results are summarized in Fig. 8(c). Similar to compressive strength, less than 10 wt% replacement leads to a small decrease in flexural strength.

5.2.2.4. Elastic modulus. The effect of reinforcing concrete with macrofibers on the elastic modulus seems negligible upon small (≤ 2 vol. %) reinforcement levels reported in the literature. Generally, the ascending branches of the compressive stress–strain curves are similar, regardless of the presence of fibers. Thus, a limited amount of macrofibers (≤ 2.5 vol%) have a negligible effect on concrete elasticity. However, the post-peak softening branch of the compressive stress–strain curve changes drastically when macrofibers are present in the concrete mix. A smoother post-peak stress decay can be observed, when compared

against that of conventional concrete, attributed to the macrofiber bridging the wing-cracks, making the concrete mix more ductile by preventing sudden cracking of the material. Yazdanbakhsh et al. [82] reported a slight increase (6–12%) in the elastic modulus of concrete reinforced with 100 mm long needle elements for most cases investigated, in which the elastic modulus of control sample, PLN-5, and PLN-10 are 25.9, 29.1, and 5.8 GPa, respectively. Here PLN represents plain needles of WTBW. The sharp edge of the WTBW needles may lead to a stronger bond with cementitious mortar increasing the elastic modulus. However, a slight reduction (4.7%) was determined for the 10% CA replacement using grooved needles, might be attributed to the direction of the fibers.

5.2.2.5. Toughness. As with the addition of fibers, the toughness of the resulting mixture is greatly enhanced as a consequence of the fiber bridging effect enhancing post-peak energy absorption when slender fiber-like aggregates are incorporated into the matrix [82,94]. Yazdanbakhsh et al. [82] reported that the incorporation of needle-like aggregates into the matrix at volumetric dosages of 5% and 10% causes the toughness to increase to 14.1 J and 33.3 J, respectively, from a value of 1.2 J in the control mixture. It is expected that if the wind blade shell is cut along the fibers, ensuring that the fibers in all the needles are longitudinally aligned, the flexural resistance of the beam specimens would significantly increase.

5.2.3. Cement replacement

Using WTBW powder as a replacement for cement has considerable potential thanks to the material's pozzolanic activity [95,96]. Additionally, the “filling effect”, whereby the smaller particles fill voids or gaps in the microstructure of cementitious systems, thus increasing their mechanical strength [90], also raises the confidence levels within the research community regarding the efficiency of potential cement replacement by WTBW powder. However, relevant published research is

significantly limited. The effect of WTBW on concrete properties as powder replacement is summarized in Fig. 9 including compressive strength and flexural strength. The detailed discussion is presented as follows.

5.2.3.1. Compressive strength. Baturkin et al. [18] investigated the applicability of WTBW powder as a potential substitute for cement in the size range of 3 μm (smaller than cement) and replacement levels of 10%, 20%, and 30% by weight. Baturkin et al. [18] argued that the organic content (29% resin and 7% wood) of WTBW powder leads to a drop in mechanical strength, while an increase in the retarding properties is also expected due to the presence of cellulose in wood. The results showed that incorporating the WTBW powder, without further treatment and removal of the organic content, significantly reduced the 28-day compressive strength. More specifically, 26%, 64%, and 67% decay were observed for 10%, 20%, and 30% cement replacement, respectively. The corresponding drop for the post-wood removal specimens was 16% at 10% cement replacement, demonstrating a more competitive performance. The results are shown in Fig. 9(a). It is worth noting that using filtered WTBW within the concrete mix was observed to maintain compressive strength compared to plain concrete at 90 days at low cement replacement levels (10 wt%).

5.2.3.2. Flexural strength. Compared to compressive strength, flexural strength was less affected when part of the cement was replaced by WTBW powder. Baturkin et al. [18] revealed an average of 6% drop in flexural strength for every 10% cement mass being replaced ($\sim 18\%$ drop in flexural strength at 30% w/w replacement). The difference between compressive and flexural strength trends can be explained by the shape of the WTBW parts used in the mix designs. Baturkin et al. [18] reported that even after fine crushing, a preference for non-ground fibrous WTBW particles was observed in the powder mix, serving as micro-reinforcements in the matrix. The results for flexural strength are shown in Fig. 9(b).

6. Comparison against surrogate cases & extended scenarios

In this chapter, the results presented in the previous section are compared against surrogate case studies associated with GFRPs, not relevant to WTBW. Supplementary studies performed on non-clinker composites are included to highlight the wide range of applications within the construction industry.

6.1. Comparison between WTBW and non-WTBW related GFRPs used in cementitious composites

The previous sections focused on isolating and presenting the results of the study cases launched separately to explore the potential of using

WTBW in cementitious formulations under various concepts and approaches. The two predominant philosophies can be divided into the replacement concept, focusing on reducing natural resources and cement usage to constrain the carbon footprint, and the reinforcement concept, liaising with the potential of utilizing fibrous materials to improve the mechanical properties and the principle mix design. The studies presented in the previous sections, separated for the sake of simplicity and uniformity, are all summarized in Fig. 10 and Table 3. The results associated with the replacement concept are illustrated in Fig. 10(a) and (b), while those relevant to reinforcement are shown in Fig. 10(c) and (d). Results for both compressive and bending testing programs are given. Legends in all figures describe the applied mix design launched for each study. The legend format initiates with the first author and year of the corresponding publication, followed by the phase replaced by WTBW (i.e., CemRep stands for cement replacement, and AggRep stands for coarse aggregate replacement). The last part of the legend format described the product material (i.e., concrete, mortar) and an abbreviation for the physical state of the WTBW (i.e., MSP stands for mechanically shredded powder, and MSF stands for mechanically shredded fiber).

Comparing the investigated cases of the replacement concept, coarse aggregate replacement seems the most efficient method, compared to cement and sand, since a drop in compressive strength is more constrained for an equal percentage of material replaced. It is, though, important to clarify that comparing different mix design protocols could lead to erroneous results, and therefore, such observations and conclusions should be treated with caution. The linear drop observed in flexural strength with increasing replacement levels seems more uniform, regardless of the replacement phase.

The compressive strength (Fig. 10(a)) decreases consistently with increasing replacement levels of conventional materials with WTBW. This trend highlights the reduction in mechanical performance at higher replacement levels, likely due to the weaker bonding or lower reactivity of WTBW compared to the original materials. The flexural strength (Fig. 10(b)) shows a noticeable reduction as the replacement percentage of conventional materials with WTBW increases. This behavior indicates that the structural integrity under bending stress is compromised at higher replacement levels, which could be attributed to changes in the matrix composition and interfacial bonding.

The accumulated results discussing utilizing macrofibers to reinforce cementitious components exhibit considerable uniformity. Compressive strength is retained in most studies, even though an insignificant decay with rising portions of incorporated material can be noted. The compressive strength (Fig. 10(c)) exhibits a slight improvement at lower fiber replacement levels (vol. %), reflecting the ability of WTBW fibers to enhance crack resistance. However, beyond a certain replacement level, the strength begins to decline, which may be due to challenges in fiber dispersion or reduced matrix integrity. The flexural strength (Fig. 10(d)) increases significantly at low fiber replacement levels, demonstrating

Fig. 9. Effect of using WTBW powder as cement replacement on (a) compressive strength and (b) flexural strength of cementitious composites (concrete).

Fig. 10. Cumulative results with WTBW into cementitious composites corresponding to the replacement concept (compressive and flexural strength changes (a) and (b)) and reinforcement concept (compressive and flexural strength changes (c) and (d)).

the beneficial effects of WTBW fibers in enhancing toughness and crack-bridging capacity. At higher replacement volumes, the flexural strength stabilizes or slightly decreases, possibly due to reduced fiber–matrix interaction, as mentioned compatibility issue in Section 4.2.

Similar concepts (replacement and reinforcement) have been implemented and investigated for various materials, including plastic composites, i.e., polycarbonate (PC), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polypropylene (PP), and polystyrene (PS) [88]. Within the corresponding pilot studies, plastic composites were used either in the form of aggregates or fibers. In addition to conventional plastic polymers, glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) material has also been presented as a potential solution for eco-friendly cementitious formulations in powder and fibers (as shown in Fig. 11 and Table 4). Asokan et al. [88] produced partially (5% up to 50%) concrete specimens, replacing sand with GFRP powder from the roofing and cladding industry. The as-received mixture was inhomogeneous, containing macrofibers of various sizes and powder particles. Sieving and fiber-powder segregation were performed to finally acquire fine powder with particle sizes ranging from 0.02 to 600 μm . Thermoset polyester resin was detected during powder chemical characterization. Dehghan et al. [97] explored the potential of utilizing various types of recycled GFRP waste material in cementitious formulations and accumulating the same benefits as those achieved via incorporating conventional fibers. Structural sheet molding composites were used for this study, with the type of encapsulated resin varying (vinyl ester, unsaturated polyester). The w/c ratio remained identical in all mix designs, while both coarse aggregates and sand were partially replaced with GFRP powder/macrofiber mix in comparison to the reference/control GFRP-free specimens. The average fiber cluster length varied from ~ 17 mm to ~ 25 mm, while the organic compounds ranged from 46% to 59%. Correia et al. [89] conducted an extensive experimental program to evaluate the

strength and durability of concrete specimens where the sand was partially (up to 20%) replaced by sand. The waste material partially substitutes the sand, consisting of extremely fine GFRP particles ($< 63 \mu\text{m}$) originating from cutting pultruded profiles. Ribeiro et al. [98] utilized residuals originating from the cutting and shredding GFRP pultrusion profiles to execute the research experimental program. GFRP material consisted of an unsaturated polyester resin ($\sim 29\%$ organic content). The residuals were further processed via grinding, milling, and sieving and were ultimately segregated into the coarse-fibrous (average particle diameter of 950 μm) and the fine-powdered (average particle diameter of 390 μm) parts. The fabricated specimens were subjected to monotonic compressive and flexural testing. Titarelli et al. [87] adopted a similar concept of replacing sand with GFRP waste within the cementitious matrix and evaluating the corresponding effect on the material performance. The waste incorporated within the produced specimens was predominantly in powder form with an average particle size of 80 μm , while a limited proportion of fibers (maximum length 20 mm) was also present. Thermoset polyester resin (80% organic material) was identified via FTIR spectroscopy, while thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) revealed a 20% by volume of glass fibrous material. Several mix designs were fabricated with sand replacement levels ranging from 10% to 20% by volume. The implemented experimental protocol included drying shrinkage and compressive and flexural testing. Garcia et al. [99] explored the effect of using mechanically recycled GFRP macro-fibrous elements as a sand replacement (1%–2%) on the workability and strength of mortar specimens. Utilizing segregated macrofibers instead of coarse or fine pulverized material slightly differentiates this study from similar concepts presented in the previous about GFRP-waste replacing sand in cementitious formulations. The GFRP waste material originated from various sources, including streamlined fairings on trains, electrical panel boards, and pultruded GFRP profiles; the organic

Table 3
Valorizing GFRP waste in cementitious materials: applied concepts and representative chemical and physical properties.

Author	Material	Applied Concept	Material Replaced	% of Replacement/ Reinforcement	Organic Composition	Raw Material Particle Size (µm)	Average MacroFiber Length/ Width/Thickness (mm)	Raw Material Density (g/cm ³)
WTBW								
1.Baturkin (2021) [18]	Concrete	Replacement	Cem ^a	10–30 w/w	36 %	3	–	1.66
2.Baturkin (2021) [18]	Concrete	Replacement	CA ^b	33–100 vol	36 %	3	–	1.66
3.Baturkin (2021) [18]	Concrete	Reinforcement	–	1 & 1.75 vol	36 %	3	NR ^c	1.66
4.Yazdanbakhsh (2018) [82]	Concrete	Replacement	CA	5 & 10 vol	NR	NR	–	NR
5.Oliveira (2020) [32]	Mortar	Replacement	FA ^d	7.5–37.5 w/w	23.80 %	NR	–	NR
6.Plawecka (2020)	Geopolymer	Reinforcement	–	5–15 vol	27–43 %	–	0.05–1/-/-	NR
7.R.Cuesta (2023)	Concrete	Replacement	Cem/CA/FA	1.7 & 6.6 vol	34 %	NR	13/0.73/0.73 ^e	1.63
8.Xu (2022)	Concrete	Reinforcement	–	0.5–2.5 vol	NR	–	47.2/3.64/0.97	1.82
9.Rodin III (2018)	Mortar	Replacement	FA	1.8–9.2 w/w	43 %	NR	–	1.76
10.Fu (2021)	Concrete	Reinforcement	–	0.5–1.5 vol	NR	–	89.7/3.04/0.79	1.97
11.Senff (2020)	Geopolymer	Reinforcement	–	1.0–2.0 vol	NR	–	6/0.018/0.018 ^e	NR
Non-WTBW GFRP								
1.Asokan (2009) [88]	Concrete	Replacement	FA	5–50 w/w	NR	0.02–600	0.02–20	–
2.Asokan (2010) [86]	Concrete	Replacement	FA	5–15 w/w	NR	0.02–600	0.02–20	–
3.Dehghan (2017) [97]	Concrete	Reinforcement	–	1.4 vol	46–59 %	0.02–600	19.5–21.7/-/-	1.56–1.66
4.Correia (2011) [89]	Concrete	Replacement	FA	5–20 w/w	NR	10	–	1.84
5.Ribeiro (2015) [98]	Mortar	Replacement	FA	4–12 w/w	29 %	390	–	NR
6.Garcia (2014)	Mortar	Replacement	FAFA	1–2 w/w	33–69 %	NR	6–12/-/-	1.45–1.96
7.Tittarelli (2010)	Mortar	Replacement	–	10–20 w/w	80 %	80	0.02–20/-/-	1.3

- a. Cem stands for Cement.
- b. CA stands for Coarse Aggregates.
- c. NR stands for Not Reported.
- d. FA stands for Fine Aggregates.
- e. Width and Thickness are replaced by equivalent diameter.

Fig. 11. Cumulative results corresponding to the replacement concept, summarizing the studies incorporating GFRP not relevant to WTBW into cementitious materials. Compressive and flexural strength changes for various replacement levels are given in (a) and (b).

content of GFRP recyclates ranged between 33% – 69%, depending on the origin source, while the length amplitude of microfibers encapsulated within the cementitious mix was 6–12 mm. Part of the results reported in the above experimental studies, only focusing on the replacement concept, were collected and presented in Fig. 11.

The performance of cementitious composites with GFRP waste also depends on its source, composition, and processing. GFRP from wind turbine blades, with higher glass fiber content (around 65%), showed

better strength compared to shipyard waste (with around 20%) [87]. Meanwhile, pultruded GFRP with aligned fibers improved reinforcement, whereas randomly oriented fibers distributed stress more uniformly but with reduced strength. Fine GFRP particles (<150 µm) enhanced packing and compressive strength, while coarser particles (1–2 mm) acted as sand replacements but weakened bonding [92]. These results emphasize the need to optimize GFRP waste properties for effective use in cementitious composites.

Table 4
 Valorizing GFRP waste in cementitious materials: applied concepts and detailed explanation.

Author	Material	Applied Concept	Material Replaced	Nomenclature Raw Material	Explanation
WTBW					
1.Baturkin (2021) [18]	Concrete	Replacement	Cem ^a	WTBW-GFRP-MSP	Powder replace cement (3 um)
2.Baturkin (2021) [18]	Concrete	Replacement	CA ^b	WTBW-GFRP-CA	Cut off cubic pieces
3.Baturkin (2021) [18]	Concrete	Reinforcement	–	WTBW-GFRP-MSFR	Selected macrofibers – no extra information given
4.Yazdanbakhsh (2018) [82]	Concrete	Replacement	CA	WTBW-GFRP-CA	Cut off cylindrical pieces
5.Oliveira (2020) [32]	Mortar	Replacement	FA ^d	WTBW-GFRP-MS	Powder to replace sand – size not reported
6.R.Cuesta (2023) [20]	Concrete	Replacement	Cem/CA/FA	WTBW-GFRP-MS	Powder + fibers mix replacing both CA & Sand
7.Xu (2022) [76]	Concrete	Reinforcement	–	WTBW-GFRP-MSFR	Selected macrofibers – reinforcement 47.2/3.64/0.97
8.Rodin (2018) [92]	Mortar	Replacement	FA	WTBW-GFRP-MSFR	Selected macrofibers – sand replacement NR
9.Fu (2021) [77]	Concrete	Reinforcement	–	WTBW-GFRP-MSFR	Selected macrofibers – reinforcement 89.7/3.04/0.79
Non-WTBW GFRP					
1.Asokan (2009) [88]	Concrete	Replacement	FA	GRP-MS	Mix of fibers and powder/ Not selected
2.Asokan (2010) [86]	Concrete	Replacement	FA	GRP-MS	Mix of fibers and powder/ Not selected
3.Deaghan (2017) [97]	Concrete	Reinforcement	–	GFRP-MSFR	Mix of fibers and powder/ Not selected
4.Correia (2011) [89]	Concrete	Replacement	FA	GFRP-MSP	Selected Powder (10um)
5.Ribeiro (2015) [98]	Mortar	Replacement	FA	GFRP-MS	Not selected Powder (390um)
6.Garcia (2014)	Mortar	Replacement	FAFA	GFRP-MSFR	Selected macrofibers – sand replacement 6–12 mm
7.Tittarelli (2010)	Mortar	Replacement	–	GFRP-MS	Mix of fibers and powder/ Not selected

a. Cem stands for Cement.

b. CA stands for Coarse Aggregates.

c. NR stands for Not Reported.

d. FA stands for Fine Aggregates.

e. Width and Thickness are replaced by equivalent diameter.

Notes:

- Replacement or reinforcement has to do with the amount of material used extra or no.

- MSFR stands for selected macrofibers subsequently used for a specific reason, e.g. reinforcement.

- Sometimes, a mix of macrofibers and powder is used without pre-selection.

A direct comparison between the performance of cementitious materials incorporating WTBW-GFRP waste (Fig. 10) and those containing non-WTBW-GFRP waste (Fig. 11) is summarized in Fig. 12, where applicable.

The conclusions drawn from Fig. 11 are similar to those reported for the cumulative results presented in Fig. 10, corresponding to cementitious products incorporating WTBW. All the studies presented in Fig. 11 correspond to sand replacement scenarios. A general trend of progressive loss of compressive strength while partly substituting increasing portions of sand with GFRP powder can be observed. However, it is evident that compressive strength is sometimes retained and even increases at low replacement levels. Such an observation was also noted for a limited part of the corresponding studies utilizing WTBW for replacement, albeit not to such a distinct extent. This positive outcome of compressive strength reinforcement, partially noted in Fig. 11(a), is also extended while monitoring the effect of GFRP incorporation in mortar specimen flexural strength. In most of those cases, a slight increase can be observed. This is attributed to microfibers within the GFRP material used for encapsulation and completely pulverized particles. Without neglecting the importance of variation in mix designs, materials used, and testing protocols, the results relevant to non-WTBW-waste GFRP materials are slightly more promising than WTBW-waste encapsulation. This conclusion can designate the need for further studies on WTBW material, focusing on waste characterization to reveal the optimum treatment process, leading to enhanced properties of the final cementitious product. The presence of deleterious substances within the shredded components, i.e., balsa wood, which could be linked with the poor performance of the final product, has already been demonstrated in the literature [18].

6.2. WTBW-GFRP used in non-clinker composites

WTBW-GFRP and recycled GFRP (GF) of different origins are used as an aggregate replacement, reinforcement, and filler for non-clinker inorganic circular composites as shown in Fig. 13. The primary research areas for non-clinker binders are gypsum-based composites [100], synthetic gypsum (phosphogypsum) [101], geopolymers

[81,102], mortars [103] and foams [95] based on them. The studies considered below (shown in Fig. 13) mostly demonstrate the positive impact of recycled fiber on the mechanical properties of the composites and preventing pure brittle behavior, as was observed for cement-based composites.

6.2.1. Gypsum-based composites

It can be seen in Fig. 13 (a) and (b), Gonçalves et al. [101] considered using recycled fiber from GFRP sheets for gypsum composites. Recycled fiber was obtained by mechanical treatment (crushing in domestic bio-crusher) and subsequent sieving. The results of testing gypsum composites demonstrate the increase in flexural strength compared to control specimens increased by 66% at a 6% dosage of recycled fiber by weight compared to 290% and 12% correspondingly for composite with virgin E-fiber, explained by better dispersion and higher adhesion to the gypsum matrix at the absence epoxy resin coating.

The treated WTBW-GFRP was used as a component of phosphogypsum (PG) composites [101]. The waste fiber was obtained into two stages: the first one is a mechanical treatment stage consisting of cutting into blocks, crushing, shredding, and pulverization in a mill; and the second stage is sieving, washing with deionized water, and drying at 80°C. The fiber was treated with dopamine, a mixture of dopamine with terephthalic, cinnamic, and benzonitrile, resulting in improved reactivity and hydrophilicity. The dosage of fiber varied up to 2.5%. Due to the increase in the compactness of the matrix, increasing flexural and compressive strength and reduction in porosity were observed. The highest mechanical properties increase was achieved at the 2% dosage of GFRP modified by dopamine hydrochloride and 3,4-dihydroxy benzonitrile – 61% and 26% for flexural and compressive strength correspondingly comparing control samples.

6.2.2. Geopolymer-based composites

Plawecka et al. [81] used three types of WTBW-GFRP for adding as a filler but, in fact, as a partial sand replacement and reinforcement of geopolymer (as shown in Fig. 14(a) and (b)). Two GFRP fractions (I and III) were from the aerodynamic part of WTBW (powder + fiber mix), and one (II) was from the monolithic part of WTBW (powder). The main

Fig. 12. Cumulative results corresponding to the replacement concept, summarizing the studies incorporating WTW-related and GFRP waste from other industries unrelated to WTW into cementitious materials. (a)compressive strength; (b)flexural strength.

geopolymer components were river sand and fly ash, a mix of sodium water glass, and an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide, which was used as an alkaline activator. It was demonstrated that at WTBW-GFRP content 5–15% by weight, it is possible to achieve compressive and flexural strength compatible with control specimens without waste. Compared to the control, there is a significant reduction in compressive strength and increasing absorbability of the specimens with wastes. The compressive strength for all the dosages 5–30% by geopolymer is lower than for control; however, at 5~15% dosage of WTBW-GFRP of III type, the compressive and flexural strength of the specimen is compatible with the control.

The study by Senff et al. [95] on using WTBW-GF as reinforcement in

geopolymer foams demonstrates the possibility of obtaining non-structural application material. The main components of the geopolymer were metakaolin, biomass fly ash, sodium silicate + NaOH as an alkaline activator, aluminum powder as a foaming agent, and foam stabilizing agent. Results demonstrate that the fiber incorporation effectively enhances the geopolymer foam mortars' flexural (up to 23%) and compressive strength (up to 30%) compared with the un-reinforced foams. The thermal conductivity of geopolymer foam is about 3 times lower than for geopolymers. The impact of WTBW-GFRP for that parameter is not significant. Therefore, the WTBW-GP significantly improves mechanical properties without effects on thermal conductivity.

Fig. 13. Effect of WTBW as fiber reinforcement on the (a) flexural and (b) compressive strength of gypsum-based composites at 7 days (PBGC = phosphorous-building gypsum composites; UWF = unmodified waste glass fiber; MWF = modified waste glass fiber; NGF = new glass fibers).

Fig. 14. Effect of WTBW as powder replacement on the (c) flexural and (d) compressive strength of geopolymers at 28 days.

Zheng et al. [103] investigated the impact of partial replacement of ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBS) for GFRP powder for geopolymer repairing mortars, which is presented. GFRP powder was

applied as a component binding agent and activated by an alkaline solution. The increase in GFRP powder replacement led to the rise in the setting time of geopolymer mortar due to GGBS reactivity mitigation

Fig. 15. Discussion and future perspectives.

and decreased the workability of mortars. Adding 20% of GFRP led to achieving the highest compressive and flexural strength values within the 20–50% range. There is a significant increase in the ductility of geopolymers. An optimal composition can be applied to repair mortar according to the standards, and even higher GFRP /GGBS-based GM has a higher modulus of rupture than cement-FA-based mortar.

Considering the possible widening of the area of non-clinker-based composites application of WTBW-GFRP, the impact of these wastes on gypsum-based binders and gypsum and synthetic gypsum foams should be mentioned. The effect of different sizes and shapes of WTBW-GBRP on geopolymer mortars and foams is also a potential area of research.

7. Future perspectives and environmental impact

Utilizing WTBW as additives in concrete production presents a promising avenue for sustainable construction practices. The potential research directions are shown in Fig. 15.

7.1. WTBW reactivity and its implications on the hydration process

Glass fiber, a major component in WTBW, contains large amounts of reactive silica, which is beneficial to the hydration process of cementitious materials. Several factors influence the reactivity (or dissolution) of glass within a cementitious environment:

(1) Alkalinity: The alkalinity of the environment strongly influences the dissolution behavior of glass content. Alkaline conditions promote the hydrolysis of silicate bonds in the glass structure, releasing Si-O tetrahedra ($\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$) and other soluble components.

(2) Temperature: Temperature plays a significant role in dissolving glass content from recycled WTBW. Normally, higher temperatures accelerate the dissolution kinetics by increasing the system's energy.

(3) The Al/Si Ratio: The ratio of aluminum (Al) to silicon (Si) in the glass composition can affect its reactivity and dissolution behavior. Glasses with higher Al/Si ratios dissolve faster due to the weaker Al-O bond than the Si-O bond.

(4) Particle Size: The particle size of recycled WTBW also influences its reactivity and dissolution kinetics. Smaller particles have a higher specific surface area, which increases the dissolution rate. The reactivity of glass content from recycled WTBW is influenced by various factors, including temperature, alkalinity, Al/Si ratio, and particle size. Understanding the reactivity of glass content, particularly its dissolution behavior, is essential for the influence of glass in cementitious materials.

Due to the reactive silica in the glass fiber, WTBW poses the threat of alkali-silica reaction (ASR). ASR is a chemical process where alkali cations interact with hydroxyl ions within the pore solution of hydrated cement paste and with specific reactive silica phases found in the aggregates utilized in concrete. It is a long-term durability issue for aggregates in concrete. When using the WTBW as aggregates in concrete, the alkali cations interact with dissolved silicate monomers from glassy WTBW content. Consequently, the ASR could happen, causing the expansion of the concrete matrix. Internal cracking can develop within the matrix, damaging the concrete. Understanding the ASR is important for the ASR mitigation of using WTBW aggregates in concrete.

Epoxy resin, another major component in WTBW, is a kind of organic material that may hinder the hydration process of cementitious materials. Once it is incorporated into cementitious materials, the reactivity of the epoxy resin should be considered. The reactivity (or hydrolysis) of epoxy resin within a cement environment is influenced by several factors:

(1) pH Level: Higher pH levels in cementitious environments enhance the reactivity of epoxy resin due to increased epoxide ring-opening reactions.

(2) Temperature and moisture: Elevated temperatures and moisture content accelerate the rate of ring-opening reactions, promoting resin degradation.

(3) Presence of accelerators: additives such as accelerators in cement

formulations can further catalyze epoxide ring-opening reactions, expediting resin breakdown. The reactivity of epoxy resin from recycled wind turbine blade waste is influenced by various environmental factors, including epoxide ring-opening reactions in cementitious environments and hydrolysis under conditions of moisture exposure.

Understanding these mechanisms is crucial for assessing the hydration process of WTBW in cementitious materials. Indeed, the presence of epoxy resin in these waste materials introduces complexities to the concrete mix. It's imperative to delve into how epoxy resin affects the hydration process in concrete when using recycled wind turbine blade waste. Epoxy resin from WTBW contains epoxide groups susceptible to chemical reactions, especially in alkaline environments like concrete. These epoxide groups undergo hydrolysis and ring-opening responses when exposed to cementitious materials. The hydrolysis of epoxide groups consumes water and generates secondary hydroxyl groups. This process may influence the hydration kinetics of the cementitious materials. Epoxide ring-opening reactions and subsequent hydrolysis can change the chemical composition of pore solution in the concrete mix and slow the hydration process. Understanding these dynamics is vital for optimizing the utilization of recycled materials in concrete production.

It is worth noting that the durability of each produced WTBW-containing cementitious matrix should be further explored as perspectives on reinforcement or replacement concepts. For the reinforcement concept, the fiber length and content of WTBW fibers in the cementitious matrix have been extensively discussed in this study at Section 5.1, the influence of fiber orientation on the mechanical properties remains underexplored. Fiber orientation may result in isotropic mechanical properties, which is an important factor to consider. One big challenge is that resins are difficult to identify using both X-ray computed tomography (XCT) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) due to their low density. This presents difficulties in accurately locating the distribution of WTBW fibers within the cementitious matrix. Therefore, further investigations into the role of fiber orientation and its effect on mechanical properties are necessary to better understand the reinforcement potential of WTBW fibers. Also, the shrinkage test can be considered when using WTBW fibers in the cementitious matrices. For the replacement concept, WTBW contains siliceous glass, which may react with alkalis in the pore solution. This reaction could lead to expansion over time. Therefore, alkali-silica reaction (ASR) tests should be considered when using WTBW as sand or coarse aggregate. Additionally, using WTBW as a binder replacement involves different chemical reaction processes, as discussed, and may influence microstructure evolution. Permeability and rapid chloride migration (RCM) tests are essential to evaluate the long-term performance of the WTBW-containing matrix. Beyond these mentioned durability tests, further assessments should be conducted to account for the incorporation of new materials into cementitious matrices.

7.2. Discussing the environmental impact of WTBW concrete

There is a rising trend in the manufacture of WTBs in line with EU targets of increasing renewable energy and wind power production by 2050 [104]. Additionally, with repowering projects come larger turbines with longer and heavier blades, implying an even bigger volume of WTBs than the number of WTBs. The projections show that 325,000 t of WTB will be decommissioned and treated as waste by 2050, with 76% originating from onshore and 24% offshore [105]. The valorization of WTBW in concrete is potentially a sustainable solution compared to other end-of-life options for WTBs. Environmental and economic impacts of this could be quantified with lifecycle assessments (LCA) if sufficient, good-quality, and comparable data exist. Adopting lifecycle thinking, it is possible to study the impacts of different end-of-life recycling activities for WTBs, the effects of material replacement and reinforcement strategies in cement and concrete manufacture, and the impacts of use and end-of-life scenarios for WTBW-concrete. Those

impacts can be assessed alone or in combination, depending on the goal and scope of the study.

Landfill – the amount of space taken up by WTBs is a significant issue and is the most common practice at the end-of-life stage of a WTB. It is environmentally the least favored waste treatment method because there is no material or energy recovery – and contradicts the Circular Economy Action Plan advanced by the European Commission [106]. It burdens the environment, possibly contaminating soil and water for hundreds of years as blades contain non-biodegradable materials [107]. From a resources point of view, landfilling results in the diversion of great volumes of materials from the economy, as well as land loss [108]. Many countries restrict landfilling and opt for recycling solutions [109]. End-of-life recycling options for WTBs are limited because recycling technologies that can be used for WTBs are mostly low in their technological readiness levels (TRL) and their development primarily depends on the quantification and source of WTB waste streams and proven overall commercial advantages [22]. The uncertainties in these data and the absence of effective recycling infrastructures hinder the development of meaningful scenarios and functional unit definitions for LCA.

Research on material replacement and reinforcement strategies in cement and concrete is common. Most of this research regarding WTB use in composite materials focuses on physical and mechanical properties, processability, and alike [32,81,82,104,110–112]. The environmental impacts are considered less frequently but can be found in the literature [113–118]. Decarbonization in cement and concrete materials mainly happens through the clinker-to-cement ratio reduction via the use of blended materials and alternative binding materials use [119,120]. The largest carbon footprint in concrete is attributed to Ordinary Portland Cement, particularly the calcination of limestone and the combustion of fossil fuels during the clinker firing phase to reach approximately 1450 °C temperature in the kiln [121]. Therefore, the two major environmental impact indicators in cement and concrete production are energy demand and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Reduction of these could benefit from optimized resource use from a whole system perspective so that the materials used in concrete are obtained or supplied from other industries as long as feasible. As such, using mechanically recycled WTBW as part of reinforcement and replacement strategies in concrete manufacture represents reductions in raw material extraction, leading to substantial energy savings and carbon footprint reduction in the concrete industry. For instance, a recent study shows that global warming potential (GWP) of fiber-reinforced concrete could be reduced up to 94%, without hindering its mechanical performance [118]. This value is highly dependent on the fibers used and it is promising to investigate the contribution of WTBW in concrete sustainability both as reinforcement and replacement.

There is broad acknowledgment that concrete production heavily relies on using finite resources that inflict high environmental impacts during raw material extraction and manufacturing. The two major environmental impact indicators are energy demand and GHG emissions. It is thus essential to optimize resource use from a whole system perspective so that the materials used in concrete production are obtained or supplied with a circular economy in mind. As such, recycled WTBs in cement replacement or aggregates as secondary materials in concrete manufacture represent large reductions in cement or aggregate production. It leads to substantial energy savings and carbon footprint reduction in the concrete industry.

The role of the use phase in a WTBW-concrete lifecycle is multifaceted. The function of the concrete in its particular use and the conditions it is exposed to are crucial. If the designed performance—such as structural, hygrothermal, and fire protection—does not meet the target values, and if the concrete deteriorates or is easily damaged, it will require more maintenance and repair interventions. However, maintenance and repair interventions account for a significant portion of the total environmental impacts and economic costs of a concrete structure throughout its lifespan [113]. Thus, it is imperative to define the end-use

for the WTBW-concrete, whether it is structural or non-structural, exposed to atmospheric conditions, or remains in a relatively stable indoor environment, and determine other factors that influence its durability. Using WTBW in concrete can help reduce the carbon footprint by lowering the amount of cement required [122]. Adding WTBW as an overall supplement in concrete reduces the cement content per cubic meter, which is beneficial since cement is the component with the highest carbon footprint in concrete [122]. Studies have shown that concrete mixes containing WTBW have a lower Global Warming Potential (GWP) compared to traditional fiber-reinforced concrete [123]. For example, using 1% WTBW by volume can reduce GWP by up to 51.48% compared to concrete with steel fibers. Incorporating WTBW as a substitute for aggregates or as fiber reinforcement reduces the demand for natural aggregates, thereby lowering energy consumption and environmental impact. Additionally, producing Raw-Crushed Wind-Turbine Blade (RCWTB) is 41% cheaper in energy costs compared to the average energy consumption for quarrying natural crushed aggregate [123]. Cutting and crushing the blades into smaller particles require approximately 1.23 kWh per metric ton, costing about €0.25 per metric ton in Spain. The valorization of WTBW in concrete affects the concrete properties and results in a certain behavior, eventually impacting its service life and the frequency of interventions. To conclude if WTBW-concrete is environmentally sustainable or not, one should carry out LCA studies taking into account different use phase scenarios.

Typical end-of-life scenarios for concrete are mechanical recycling, reuse in its original form, and disposal in landfills. Although recycling concrete and using it as aggregates (RCA) is gaining traction as a sustainable alternative [124], the environmental studies on concrete indicate that the end-of-life stage often involves significant uncertainty, which is affected by the methods of demolition and disposal used [125]. For today, the same end-of-life scenarios are valid for WTBW-concrete, however, with higher uncertainty. The effects of WTBW valorization in concrete regarding the separation of mixed waste materials at the end of the WTBW-concrete service life are unknown. This includes concerns about health and safety issues as well as whether any form of treatment is necessary. All processes come with a unique environmental impact and cost.

However, improper preparation and handling of WTBW during processing could increase its environmental impact. Therefore, conducting LCA is essential to evaluate the environmental benefits of using WTBW in concrete and to optimize its application to ensure sustainability. LCAs can provide a better understanding of the environmental impacts of incorporating recycled WTBW in concrete, including assessing the potential environmental trade-offs and benefits. This includes analyzing the influence of regional factors on the environmental performance of WTBW-based concrete, exploring the role of supplementary materials in improving sustainability, and quantifying the carbon footprint reductions achieved by recycling WTBW in concrete. These aspects offer valuable insights into the environmental impact of recycled concrete and contribute to advancing sustainable construction practices. Furthermore, the research will explore strategies (WTBW as reinforcement or replacement) to optimize the environmental benefits of incorporating recycled WTBW in concrete while ensuring structural integrity and performance standards are met.

8. Conclusions and strategic visions

This review provides, for the first time, comprehensive perspectives on using wind turbine blade waste (WTBW) in the cementitious matrix, including the reaction mechanism of WTBW in the concrete environment (which is the first time to provide the mechanism summary), the mechanistic descriptions of different types of replacement in concrete – using WTBW as reinforcement, and replacement as coarse aggregate, fine aggregate, and cement, and the environmental impact of WTBW concrete. The successful use of WTBW replacement in cementitious materials will favor both the construction and wind industry from the

perspective of circular economy.

According to the obtained literature studies and analysis, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The density of WTBW-MSP has an average of 1.6 ~ 2.0 g/cm³. Slender waste has high flexural stiffness and superior strength in tension and shear, which is suitable for fiber reinforcement in concrete. The WTBW mainly consists of glass fiber (primary SiO₂, CaO, and Al₂O₃ content) and epoxy resin (primary epoxide ring and hydroxyl functional groups). The structure of glass fiber as being primarily amorphous silica (SiO₂) with calcite present as a minor crystalline phase. The FTIR spectrum of epoxy resin shows characteristic peaks associated with different functional groups like epoxide and hydroxyl groups.
- The dissolution and gelation kinetics of the WTBW in concrete depend on fiber compositions and functional groups in the pore solutions. The presence of fibers, including epoxy resin from WTBW, can lead to higher water absorption due to the evolution of pore structure, potentially hindering the complete hydration of cement and affecting long-term strength. Epoxy resin may consume hydroxyl ions (epoxide ring-opening reaction), decreasing pH and impeding the hydration process, resulting in increased setting time and lower early strength. Additionally, incorporating epoxy resin into the cement matrix can introduce voids and weaken the interfacial transition zone, potentially reducing the mechanical properties of the concrete.
- The incorporation of WTBW in cementitious materials includes two main concepts- reinforcement (as fibers) or replacement (as powder, sand, or coarse aggregates). For the reinforcement concept, the compressive strength of the cementitious matrix decreases typically with the higher fiber additions, while the flexural strength increases with extra fiber additions. For the replacement concept, strength decreases with higher WTBW contents because the WTBW shows low reactivity and strength compared to raw cement and sand/aggregate, respectively. Low replacement percentages (up to 10%) provide the most competitive mechanical performance profiles, while performance declines beyond this threshold.
- Using WTBW in concrete is a new method in green waste management. Further studies are needed in several areas, including kinetic studies of WTBW reactivity, the effect of WTBW on the hydration process, and the determination of the environmental and cost impacts of adopting supplementary cementitious materials or aggregate replacement in concrete. Incorporating WTBW into concrete offers potential benefits such as sustainable waste management, creating more resilient and eco-friendly construction materials, and reducing landfills. However, the environmental impacts of this replacement need to be better quantified and characterized in the future. LCA and cost-benefit analysis of using WTBW in concrete production should soon have a growing scientific interest.

The management of WTB waste requires multiple approaches, as no single solution can fully address the environmental and economic challenges associated with its disposal. Various strategies, including repair for reuse in wind turbines, repurposing as construction materials, and recycling for cement co-processing, have shown potential for mitigating waste accumulation [126,127]. Additionally, applications such as panel production and combustion power generation offer alternative pathways for processing WTB waste [127,128]. None of the technologies are currently feasible or viable, and a structured second-hand market has yet to be established. Therefore, the geographical availability and demand for specific blade models remain uncertain [129]. Safety and availability must be prioritized before reusing and repurposing wind turbine blade waste in the specified area.

This review specifically focuses on the potential of incorporating WTB waste into cementitious materials, analyzing its reaction mechanisms and application strategies. However, this approach (WTB waste in

cementitious matrix) is not the sole or most effective solution. Instead, it is one option within a broader waste management framework that should be considered alongside other methods. By incorporating WTB waste into cementitious composites, this strategy can contribute to circular economy principles, but it should complement rather than replace potential/existing recycling and reuse solutions.

Ultimately, a combination of approaches tailored to regional policies, economic feasibility, and environmental impact will be necessary for sustainable WTB waste management. Future research should continue exploring scalable and environmentally responsible solutions that align with both industry needs and sustainability goals.

(Note: References in this part are not included in the methodology section.)

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Tao Liu: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Charilaos Paraskevoulakos:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Umair Abid Mughal:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Ashal Tyurkay:** Writing – review & editing. **Nataliya Lushnikova:** Writing – review & editing. **Helong Song:** Writing – review & editing. **Ceren Duyal:** Writing – review & editing. **Shashank Tumkur Karnick:** Writing – review & editing. **Florent Gauvin:** Writing – review & editing. **Ana Teresa Lima:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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